

Honey Production from Forests and Silvopastoral Systems

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Bee hives in fir forest (Photo by V. Lappa)

Beekeeping is one of the most important agricultural sectors and significantly contributes to rural economy and development. Apart from the economic benefits of the products yielded (honey, wax, royal jelly, pollen, etc.), its ecological role in maintaining biodiversity through pollination is very important.

Greece has a wide variety of ecosystems that support beekeeping. These ecosystems can be forests, meadows, fields and agroforestry systems. The products produced vary according to the vegetation and flora of the area (pine trees, oaks, fir trees, spruce trees, strawberry trees, etc.) in which the beehives are established, and the production is determined by the local environmental conditions. Beekeeping has faced various challenges in recent years, the main threats being climate change, insecticides and various other pesticides used in agriculture, monoculture, bee diseases and pests and competition from cheaper imported bee products. In addition, the state-owned status of most of the land used by beekeepers limits their ability to grow apiculture (favoring) plants and to intervene in the field.

The above-mentioned challenges can be addressed and can constitute a differentiating factor in remote areas from urban centers characterized by clean environmental conditions and rich biodiversity. One such example is the area of Agrafa in Evrytania, where organic beekeeping is practiced, as the area is dominated by forest and agroforestry systems, managed by traditional methods. In the area, mobile beehives are used, which are placed in forest and agroforestry areas according to the seasonal flowering of plants and trees. At the same time, the whole process is supported by a system of wireless cameras, hive scales and the use of geospatial data such as GPS, which allow the identification of sites with limited pollination and the selection of optimal locations for the placement of the hives. These practices are aimed at increasing productivity and ensuring high quality honey. In addition, the production of a variety of honeys such as fir honey, pine honey, chestnut honey, thyme honey, blossom honey of varying flowers, etc. is achieved. At the same time, the training of beekeepers in practices that enhance sustainable beekeeping practices is promoted. The honey produced is of excellent quality and provides beekeepers with the added value of the clean and unique environment of the area.

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Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.